

1 **Boosting the thermochemical energy storage performance**
2 **of Limestone by adding Mayenite**

3 Rehan Anwar^a, Abdullah Al Kape^a, Matteo Lusi^b, Epaminondas Voutsas^c, Antonio
4 Cammarata^{d*}, Aran Rafferty^e, M. Veronica Sofianos^{a*}

6 ^aSchool of Chemical and Bioprocess Engineering, University College Dublin, Belfield,
7 Dublin 4, Ireland

8 ^bDepartment of Chemical Sciences & Bernal Institute, University of Limerick, Limerick,
9 Ireland

10 ^cSchool of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 9 Iroon
11 Polytechniou Str., 15780 Athens, Greece

12 ^dDepartment of Control Engineering, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical
13 University in Prague, Technicka 2, 16627 Prague 6, Czech Republic.

14 ^eAMBER Research Centre, Naughton Institute, Trinity College Dublin, College Green,
15 Dublin 2, Ireland

16

17

18 E-mail: mvsofianou@gmail.com

19 E-mail: cammaant@fel.cvut.cz

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22 **Abstract**

23 Long-duration energy storage (LDES) systems play a critical role in the integration of
24 intermittent renewable energy sources into the grid. Thermochemical energy storage (TCES)
25 systems, particularly Limestone ones, offer promising solutions due Limestone's high energy
26 storage density and cost-effectiveness. However, the cycling performance of Limestone is
27 hindered by sintering phenomena and pore plugging. This paper explores the enhancement of
28 Limestone's TCES performance by incorporating Mayenite, a mesoporous ternary oxide, as
29 an additive. Mayenite can improve the cycling performance of Limestone by enhancing: (1)
30 the Ca^{2+} ion migration at high temperatures promoting the carbonation reaction and (2) the
31 CO_2 diffusion as shown by the carbonation reaction rate analysis of the mixture samples. In
32 detail, three different Mayenite samples with unique Ca to Al ratios were synthesized and
33 added to Limestone in varying concentrations. The mixture sample containing 5% Mayenite
34 (with a lower Ca to Al ratio) enhanced 2.5 times Limestone's energy storage performance
35 after 40 cycles, boosting it from 455 kJ/kg to 1137 kJ/kg. Characterization techniques
36 including X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, and thermogravimetric analysis
37 provide insights into the structural and kinetic changes induced by Mayenite addition. On the
38 other hand, Density Functional Theory Calculations showed that migration of Ca^{2+} ions is
39 promoted at high temperatures, improving the carbonation reaction of Limestone. The results
40 demonstrate the potential of Mayenite as an effective additive for improving the performance
41 of Limestone TCES systems, paving the way for more efficient and reliable long-duration
42 energy storage solutions.

43

44 **Keywords:** Long-duration energy storage, Thermochemical energy storage, Calcium
45 carbonate, Limestone, Mayenite, Cycling stability

46 **1. Introduction**

47 Long-duration energy storage (LDES) systems are essential for ensuring the seamless
48 integration of intermittent energy sources, like solar and wind power, into the energy grid [1].
49 They are devised to store large amounts of energy for prolonged periods, ranging from several
50 hours to several weeks [2]; playing a pivotal role for decarbonizing the energy grid, provide
51 grid stability, and reduce supply-demand mismatches [3, 4]. According to the way they store
52 energy, LDES systems can be categorized as mechanical (pumped hydropower and
53 compressed air energy storage) [5], electrochemical (for example redox flow batteries) [6],
54 chemical (for example hydrogen storage), thermal (for example molten salts), and
55 thermochemical (for example calcination and carbonation of Limestone) [7, 8].
56 Thermochemical energy storage systems rely on reversible chemical reactions that use thermal
57 energy to run an endothermic reaction. The stored thermal energy is then released through an
58 exothermic reaction. There are a number of thermochemical energy storage systems such as
59 carbonates, hydroxides, metal redox, sulfur, hydrides, methanol and ammonia [9]. Among
60 these thermochemical LDES systems, Limestone stands out as most promising, due to its
61 inexpensive nature (Limestone abundance), high energy density and high operating
62 temperatures (800-900 °C) offering a heat-to-power conversion efficiency at 74% [10, 11].
63 In more detail, Limestone thermochemical energy storage (TCES) systems involve the cycling
64 of Limestone (CaCO₃) between the calcination (endothermic) and carbonation (exothermic)
65 reaction in order to store and release thermal energy [12].

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70 Limestone TCES systems offer the advantage of high energy density (>1000 kJ/kg) and long
 71 energy storage duration, which can be theoretically unlimited [13]. The produced CO_2 gas
 72 can be stored in gas storage unit, whereas the CaO can be stored at an ambient temperature
 73 for an unlimited time. Their ability to store energy in the form of chemical reactions allows
 74 for efficient, reliable and scalable solutions, transforming the renewable energy sector. As the
 75 energy landscape continues to shift towards cleaner and more sustainable practices, the
 76 development of Limestone TCES systems represent a promising avenue for enhancing the
 77 viability and widespread implementation of renewable energy sources [14].

78 Fig. 1 shows a schematic of a TCES system combined with electricity generation and steam
 79 production. During the process of charging (calcination-endothermic) Limestone is converted
 80 to CaO and CO_2 , with CaO remaining in the containment vessel (reactor) as a solid while CO_2
 81 is stored separately in a gas storage unit. On the other hand, while discharging (carbonation-
 82 exothermic) CO_2 is fed back to the containment vessel to convert CaO into Limestone.
 83 During this process of discharging CO_2 can be used as the heat transfer fluid in that system to
 84 generate steam or electricity.

85
 86 **Fig. 1.** Schematic of TCES combined with electricity generation (by wind turbines, solar PV
 87 or surplus electricity from the grid) and steam production.

88 The major challenge of Limestone TCES systems is their degrading performance after a few
89 energy storage cycles. This performance degradation is linked to sintering phenomena, pore
90 plugging, and the formation of a core-shell structure of CaCO_3/CaO grains while cycling.
91 During the carbonation process, CaO (core) is encapsulated by CaCO_3 (shell), hindering the
92 diffusion of CO_2 and other ions (Ca^{2+} , O^{2-} , CO_3^{2-}) necessary to complete the carbonation
93 reaction, as CaCO_3 has a more dense matrix when compared to CaO [15].

94 The most applied method in the literature for mitigating these issues, involves the
95 introduction of additives to Limestone [15-18]. These additives function as spacers and/or
96 ionic conductors amongst the CaCO_3/CaO grain boundaries, reducing sintering phenomena,
97 pore plugging, and enhancing Ca^{2+} , O^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} mobility [15, 19]. Metal oxides are the most
98 common additives for improving thermochemical cycling of Limestone [20]. They are
99 classified as active (e.g. SiO_2 , ZrO_2 , Al_2O_3) [21-25] and inert additives (e.g. MgO , Y_2O_3 ,
100 CeO_2) [26-30] based on their interaction with CaO . Reactive additives will form a ternary
101 oxide with CaO upon cycling at high temperatures, whereas non-reactive additives will stay
102 inert under the applied cycling conditions. Amongst the reactive additives, it has been
103 demonstrated that Al_2O_3 improves the cycling performance of Limestone significantly, due to
104 its superior performance characteristics, good mechanical strength, low cost and high
105 sintering temperature (900 °C) [31]. For instance, Benitez-Guerrero *et al.* [17] reported a
106 modified Al_2O_3 - CaO composite (5-20 wt% Al_2O_3), exhibiting an effective conversion of 0.35,
107 after 20 energy storage cycles using thermogravimetric analysis. Møller *et al.* [32] used 20 wt
108 % Al_2O_3 , showing an effective conversion of 80% after 500 cycles (regeneration included)
109 using a Sieverts apparatus. During the thermochemical cycling of Limestone, Al_2O_3 reacts
110 with CaO to form ternary metal oxides ($\text{Ca}_5\text{Al}_6\text{O}_{14}$ and $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$), which then act as
111 facilitators for the movement of ions and enhance CO_2 diffusion through the layered
112 Limestone crystal structure [20]. Although Al_2O_3 indirectly improves Limestone's cycling

113 capacity, it's significant limitation is that Limestone's energy storage density is compromised
114 since a substantial amount of Limestone is consumed for the formation of these ternary
115 oxides. Having this in mind, one would anticipate that if these ternary oxides ($\text{Ca}_5\text{Al}_6\text{O}_{14}$ and
116 $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$) are directly added to Limestone instead of Al_2O_3 for thermochemical energy
117 storage, the cycling performance of Limestone would then be improved with no compromises
118 in its energy storage density since no consumption reaction would take place.

119 In general, Mayenite ($\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ or $12\text{CaO}\cdot 7\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) is a mesoporous ternary oxide, with a
120 peculiar crystal structure. Its crystal structure is composed of positively charged
121 interconnected cages per unit cell, including two units of $[\text{Ca}_{24}\text{Al}_{28}\text{O}_{64}]^{4+}$ and two free oxide
122 O^{2-} ions [33]. Its unique ability of storing O^{2-} ions makes Mayenite attractive for several
123 applications, including the partial catalytic oxidation of methane [34], catalytic VOCs
124 oxidation [35], hydrogen storage [36] and catalytic steam reforming [37].

125 In this study, Mayenite was used as an additive to Limestone for thermochemical energy
126 storage, as an alternative to Al_2O_3 , with the aim to reduce the current limitation of Al_2O_3 being
127 a reactive additive, compromising Limestone's energy storage density upon cycling. How
128 this ternary oxide additive improved the cycling performance of Limestone in relation to its
129 energy storage density was extensively explored both experimentally and computationally.

130 Mayenite was synthesized using a simple wet precipitation method. Three different Ca/Al
131 molar ratios were employed to synthesize three Mayenite samples with unique crystal
132 defects, which were then added to pure Limestone in 5, 10, 20 wt%. Our study revealed that
133 adding Mayenite significantly improved the energy storage performance of Limestone. This
134 enhancement resulted from both enhanced CO_2 diffusion and Ca^{2+} mobility at high
135 temperatures. Notably, one of the samples with 5 wt% Mayenite showed a 2.5-fold increase
136 in energy storage density (1137 kJ/kg) compared to pure Limestone after 40 cycles, and an
137 effective conversion of 0.38, 2.5 times higher than that of pure Limestone.

138

139 2. Experimental

140 Mayenite was synthesized through a straightforward one-pot wet precipitation method. Three
141 $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ samples were prepared, as detailed in Table 1. The reason for choosing Ca to Al
142 molar ratios outside the 1/1 stoichiometric ratio was to deliberately obtain Mayenite
143 nanoparticles with crystal defects, and observe how these defects effect ionic mobility at high
144 temperatures.

145

146 **Table 1**

147 Ca/Al molar ratios and sample identities

Samples	IDs	molar ratio of Ca/Al
$\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ -I	CA	1/1
$\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ -II	CCA	1.1/1
$\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ -III	CAA	1/1.1

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149 For the 1/1 Ca to Al stoichiometric ratio, 5 mmol of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (>99%, Honeywell) and an
150 equal amount of $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (98%, Sigma-Aldrich) were dissolved separately in 45 mL
151 of ethanol. The solutions were then combined under continuous stirring, and 0.06 mol of
152 NaOH (>97%, Sigma-Aldrich) in dissolved form (10 ml water + 20 ml ethanol) was
153 gradually introduced, resulting in a final solution with a NaOH molarity of 0.5 M. This
154 solution was left to age at 50 °C for 24 h with constant stirring on a hotplate, yielding white
155 precipitates. Following centrifugation at 5000 rpm for one minute, the precipitates underwent
156 two consecutive rinses with distilled water and one with ethanol. Subsequently, the rinsed
157 precipitates were dried at 110 °C for 24 h and finally calcined in a furnace at 1000 °C for 3.5
158 h with a heating rate of 3 °C/min (refer to Fig. 2.). Calcination of the precipitates is important

159 since they are amorphous upon synthesis and need heating at 1000 °C in order to crystallise to
 160 the Mayenite phase.

161

163 **Fig. 2.** Synthesis scheme for Mayenite.

164 Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples were formulated by mechanically mixing 5, 10, and 20
 165 wt% of Mayenite with Limestone (>99%, Sigma-Aldrich). This mixing process was carried
 166 out using a mortar and pestle, and the mixture samples are summarized in Table 2.

167 **Table 2**

168 Mayenite /Limestone mixture samples and their allocated sample IDs.

wt%Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ + wt%Limestone	Sample IDs
20% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -I + 80% Limestone	20CA
20% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -II + 80% Limestone	20CCA
20% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -III + 80% Limestone	20CAA
10% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -I + 90% Limestone	10CA
10% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -II + 90% Limestone	10CCA
10% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -III + 90% Limestone	10CAA
5% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -I + 95% Limestone	5CA
5% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -II + 95% Limestone	5CCA
5% Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -III + 95% Limestone	5CAA

169

170 Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the Mayenite samples were collected on a
 171 Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer equipped with a Pixel detector and a sealed tube X-ray

172 generator with a Cu cathode. Measurements between 10° and 80° degrees in 2θ were
173 collected at room temperature in a Bragg-Brentano geometry and processed with the
174 Panalytical X'Pert HighScore software. Intensity values were numerically corrected with the
175 same software to remove the $K\alpha_2$ contribution to the diffraction pattern. Sample composition,
176 cell parameters, particle size and residual strain of each phase were determined by Rietveld
177 refinement of the experimental data against the structure models of Mayenite and Limestone
178 and Calcium Hydroxide as retrieved from the inorganic database (PDF-4 Cards 04-014-8826,
179 00-004-0777 and 04-006-9149 respectively).

180 XRD patterns of Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples were obtained by a Siemens D500
181 diffractometer equipped with a Cu-K α radiation. All measurements were carried out in a 2θ
182 range of 10° to 80° degrees with step size of 0.04° , rotational speed of 30 rpm and a scan
183 speed of 1 s/step.

184 Morphological observations of all samples were conducted utilizing a scanning electron
185 microscope (SEM) model Zeiss Sigma 300. Before SEM imaging, a modest quantity of the
186 powder sample was deposited onto a carbon tape and subsequently coated with a 4 nm thick
187 layer of Pt to mitigate charging effects during SEM imaging.

188 To investigate the Mayenite nanoparticles, a high-resolution transmission electron
189 microscope (HR-TEM) was employed, utilizing a Tecnai 20 TEM with an acceleration
190 voltage of 200 kV. For the TEM observations, samples were prepared on copper grids by
191 depositing a few drops of a suspension containing Mayenite nanoparticles and ethanol.
192 Subsequently, the samples were dried under an infrared (IR) lamp for a duration of 20-30
193 seconds.

194 EDS mapping of the Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples was performed using a Hitachi
195 Regulus 8230 Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscope (FEGSEM), which was
196 integrated with an Oxford Astec 170 EDS system and controlled by the Aztec software.

197 Specific surface area analyses of the Mayenite nanoparticles were conducted employing a
198 Micromeritics Gemini VII system (Micromeritics, Nor-cross, GA, USA) through nitrogen
199 (N₂) adsorption at 77 K. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) multi-point method was
200 employed, utilizing relative pressures ranging from 0.05 to 0.30 bar. Prior to N₂ adsorption
201 analysis, all samples underwent degassing at 300 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere for 1 h. The
202 specific surface area and pore size analysis of the Limestone sample as well as the best
203 performing Mayenite/Limestone mixture sample, before and after cycling, was conducted
204 using nitrogen gas sorption analysis at 77 K using a Nova 2400e surface area analyzer
205 (Quantachrome, UK). The specific surface area was calculated from the adsorption data at
206 relative pressures between 0.10 and 0.30, by employing the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET)
207 multi-point method. Pore size distributions and pore volumes for pores <80 nm were
208 calculated using the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method from the desorption branch of the
209 isotherm. Prior to the analysis, all four samples were outgassed at 120°C under vacuum for 1
210 h.

211 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed to investigate the chemical state of
212 the Mayenite nanoparticles, utilizing a Kratos AXIS Ultra DLD X-ray photoelectron
213 spectrometer equipped with an Al-K α X-ray source (1486.7 eV) in an ultra-high vacuum
214 environment. The acquired XPS data were analysed using the Casa XPS software and
215 calibrated with reference to the surface adventitious C 1s peak at 284.5 eV.

216 Simultaneous differential scanning calorimetry and thermogravimetric analysis (DSC-TGA)
217 were conducted using a Netzsch STA 449 F5 instrument. For the thermal analysis of
218 Limestone and the Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples, a small amount of sample weighing
219 between 35 and 40 mg was placed into an alumina crucible. The sample was then heated
220 from room temperature to 1000 °C under a N₂ flow of 20 mL/min at a heat rate of 20 °C/min.
221 Upon reaching the maximum temperature, the sample was held isothermal for 30 minutes

222 under a CO₂/N₂ flow of 100 mL/min and 20 mL/min, respectively. Subsequently, the sample
223 was then cooled down to room temperature at a rate of 20 °C/min under the same
224 atmosphere.

225 The activation energy for the calcination reaction was determined using the Kissinger method
226 [38, 39], employing multiple heat rate thermal analysis measurements (Eq. (1)). In detail, the
227 sample, weighing 35-40 mg, was heated from room temperature to 950 °C at heating rates of
228 5, 10, and 20 °C/min under an N₂ flow of 20 mL/min.

$$229 \quad \ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_p^2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{AR}{E_a}\right) - \frac{E_a}{RT_p} \quad (1)$$

230 In the previous equation, β is the heating rate in K min⁻¹, T_p is the DSC peak temperature in
231 K, E_a is the apparent activation energy of the reaction in J mol⁻¹, R is the perfect gas constant
232 (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) and A is the pre-exponential factor (min⁻¹). The temperature accuracy (\pm
233 0.2 K) and the sensitivity DSC (balance accuracy \pm 0.1 μ g) were calibrated using In, Zn, Al,
234 Ag and Au reference materials.

235 A Netzsch-manufactured thermogravimetric analyzer, model STA 449 F5, was utilized for
236 conducting the calcination and carbonation cycles at a constant temperature of 850 °C. The
237 calcination process occurred under a N₂ flow of 20 mL/min for 10 minutes, while the
238 carbonation process was carried out in the presence of a gas mixture comprising carbon
239 dioxide (CO₂) and N₂ flows at rates of 100 mL/min and 20 mL/min, respectively, and
240 continued for 20 minutes. The carbonation process could not be performed under pure CO₂
241 gas, since the STA 449 F5 requires a constant N₂ flow of 20 mL/min as the balance gas.
242 Initially, all samples were subjected to heating from room temperature to 850 °C under an N₂
243 flow of 20 mL/min at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. Finally, after the completed cycles, all
244 samples were cooled down naturally to room temperature under a CO₂/N₂ flow of 100
245 mL/min and 20 mL/min, respectively.

246 The assessment of the energy storage performance of the samples involved the evaluation of
 247 their effective conversion and energy storage density. The cycling experiments were
 248 replicated thrice to ensure result reliability, the mean values and standard deviations are
 249 presented in the results section for accuracy and consistency. The effective conversion
 250 denoted as $X_{ef,N}$ was calculated as the ratio of the mass of CaO which reacted during each
 251 carbonation cycle to the total mass of the sample before carbonation, as defined by Eq. 2.
 252 This parameter serves as a crucial indicator of cycling stability and is directly proportional to
 253 the energy storage density.

$$254 \quad X_{ef,N} = \frac{m_{car,N} - m_{cal,N}}{f_{CaO} m_0} \cdot \frac{M_{CaO}}{M_{CO_2}} \quad (2)$$

255 In the context of Eq. (2), N denotes the number of calcination/carbonation cycles, and $m_{car,N}$
 256 and $m_{cal,N}$ represent the mass of the sample after the N th carbonation and N th calcination,
 257 respectively. m_0 is the original mass of the sample in g, inclusive of any additives, and f_{CaO} is
 258 the initial fraction of CaO present in the sample. M_{CaO} and M_{CO_2} denote the molar masses of
 259 CaO and CO_2 in g/mol, respectively.

260 The heat storage density, denoted as $E_{g,N}$ expresses the maximum amount of heat that can be
 261 released per unit mass of the samples during each carbonation reaction. This crucial
 262 parameter is calculated using Eq. (3) and plays a pivotal role in characterizing the heat
 263 storage performance of the samples.

$$264 \quad E_{g,N} = X_{ef,N} \cdot \frac{1000 \Delta H^\circ}{M_{CaO}} \quad (3)$$

265 In the previous equation, ΔH° is the standard enthalpy of reaction for 850 °C and equal to
 266 166.1 kJ/mol.

267 The sample's carbonation and calcination reaction rates were computed using Eq. (4) and (5)
 268 as follows:

269
$$D_N = \frac{dm_{N,t}}{m_o dt} \quad (0 < t < t_1) \quad (4)$$

270
$$R_N = \frac{dm_{N,t}}{m_o dt} \quad (t_1 < t < t_2) \quad (5)$$

271 In these equations, D_N and R_N represent the calcination and carbonation reaction rates (s^{-1})
 272 during the N th energy storage cycle, respectively. t_1 and t_2 denote the termination time (s) of
 273 the calcination and carbonation reaction, while $m_{N,t}$ represents the mass (g) of the sample at
 274 time t during the N th energy storage cycle.

275 The gas-solid reaction between CO_2 and CaO is described using the shrinking core model
 276 [40]. This model suggests that the carbonation reaction happens mainly at the outer surface of
 277 the solid CaO particle. As the reaction goes on, the unreacted core shrinks, forming a layer of
 278 $CaCO_3$. The carbonation reaction conversion is transformed into effective conversion during
 279 the calculation of carbonation kinetics. The relationships between $X_{ef,N}$ and t during the
 280 chemical reaction-controlled and diffusion-controlled phases were expressed by Eq. (6) and
 281 (7) respectively [40]:

282
$$1 - (1 - X_{ef,N})^{\frac{1}{3}} = K_C (P_{CO_2} - P_{eq}) t \quad (6)$$

283
$$1 - 3(1 - X_{ef,N})^{\frac{2}{3}} + 2(1 - X_{ef,N}) = K_D (P_{CO_2} - P_{eq}) t \quad (7)$$

284 In these equations, K_C and K_D represent the kinetic parameters during the chemical reaction-
 285 controlled and diffusion-controlled phases, respectively. P_{CO_2} and P_{eq} denote the CO_2 partial
 286 pressure and equilibrium pressure (MPa) during the carbonation reaction, where P_{eq} is
 287 calculated according to Eq. (8) [41].

288
$$\lg P_{eq} = 7.079 - \frac{8308}{T + 273} \quad (8)$$

289 T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) denotes the carbonation temperature.

290 To further understand the carbonation reaction mechanisms of the Mayenite/Limestone
291 mixture samples, computational studies were undertaken on the best performing Mayenite
292 sample CAA. In detail, the diffusion coefficients of the Ca^{2+} and O^{2-} ions for sample CAA
293 were calculated by considering a vacancy mechanism system [42]. In this, the motion of one
294 atomic species occurs by means of jumps between two neighbouring crystallographic sites of
295 the same species, where one of the two sites is not occupied, that is, it contains a vacancy.
296 The diffusion coefficient D is then calculated using Eq. 9;

$$297 \quad D(T) = \frac{k_b T}{h} f d^2 \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S_m + \Delta S_f}{k_b}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_m + \Delta H_f}{k_b T}\right)$$

298 where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, h is the Planck's constant, T is the temperature, f is the
299 correlation factor between jumps, d is the hopping distance, while ΔS_m , ΔH_m , ΔS_f , and ΔH_f are
300 the entropies and enthalpies of vacancy migration and formation, respectively.

301 In general, the enthalpy of vacancy formation is calculated as:

$$302 \quad \Delta H_f = (E_{vac} + \mu_x) - E_0 \quad (10)$$

303 where E_{vac} is the ab-initio-calculated total energy of the compound with a vacancy, μ_x is the
304 chemical potential of the missing x atom, and E_0 is the ab initio energy of the pristine
305 compound without any vacancy. The standard convention is to calculate μ_x as the ab initio
306 energy of the elemental ground state; however, in this way, the computed formation energy is
307 valid only for 0 K. Since the available experimental formation energies are typically
308 measured at room temperature or above, this leads to an estimation of the formation energies
309 which may deviate significantly from the experimental values. For this reason, to calculate
310 ΔH_f for the Ca^{2+} and O_2 species, the Open Quantum Materials Database [43] was used, which

311 corrects the ab initio energies by taking into account the available experimental data. The
312 enthalpies of vacancy migration are calculated as $\Delta H_m = E_{TS} - E_{IS}$, where E_{TS} and E_{IS} are the ab
313 initio energies of the transition state and the initial geometry configuration along the
314 migration path, respectively. The entropies of vacancy formation are calculated as $\Delta S_f = S_{IS} -$
315 S_o , where S_{IS} and S_o are the entropies of the defective system (i.e., the initial geometry
316 configuration along the migration path) and the pristine system, respectively. The entropies of
317 the ion migration are calculated as $\Delta S_m = S_{TS} - S_{IS}$, where S_{TS} and S_{IS} are the entropies of the
318 transition and the initial state, respectively. Each entropy value has been obtained by
319 postprocessing the output of the phonon calculations and applying the definition of entropy as
320 a function of the temperature in terms of phonon eigenfrequencies and population at a given
321 temperature [44].

322 Calculations were performed within the Density Functional Theory framework with the PBE
323 energy functional [45] as implemented in the VASP software [46, 47]. The Brillouin zone is
324 sampled by using a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ Monkhorst-Pack mesh and a plane-wave energy cutoff equal to
325 450 eV. The Self-Consistent Field procedure and geometry relaxations were considered
326 converged within tolerances of 10^{-8} eV and 10^{-5} eV/Å, respectively. To initiate the structural
327 relaxation of the models, the atom geometry obtained from the experimental data for sample
328 CAA was considered, which has the symmetries of the I-43d space group (S.G. no. 220). The
329 selected simulation settings reproduced the experimental geometric data with good
330 agreement. Thanks to the space group symmetries, the geometry is formed by one unique
331 crystallographic site for the Ca atom, and two distinct crystallographic sites for the Al and O
332 atoms; the latter is named as Al1 and Al2, and O1 and O2, respectively. The model geometry
333 is reported in Fig. 3.

334

335

336

337

338 **Fig. 3** Model geometry of the Mayenite phase. The distinct crystallographic sites for the Al
339 and O atoms are marked as Al1 (dark red sphere), Al2 (light green sphere), O1 (red sphere)
340 and O2 (dark green sphere), respectively. The thin black line indicates the unit cell; the
341 crystallographic axes are reported for reference.

342 The presence of a vacancy at the Ca^{2+} crystallographic site was considered; correspondingly,
343 a model system was created containing one Ca^{2+} vacancy by removing one Ca atom from the
344 pristine geometry. Analogously, the model system for the cases in which the vacancy is at the
345 O1 or at the O2 crystallographic site was built. The geometry of the as-created pristine and
346 defective structures were optimized and used to obtain the quantities involved in the
347 calculation of the diffusion coefficient. The phonopy [48] software was used to diagonalize
348 the dynamical matrices of the systems in order to obtain the phonon frequencies. Each Ca^{2+} or

349 O²⁻ crystallographic site can be occupied by an atom or a vacancy; accordingly, the following
 350 migration paths were identified: P1) Ca → Ca, P2) O1 → O1 about Al1, P3) O1 → O1 about
 351 Al2, P4) O1 → O2 about Al2. Possible O2 → O2 migration paths were not considered due to
 352 the large distance between two closest O2 sites (~5.70 Å).

353 **Fig. 4** Schematic of the (a) P1, (b) P2, (c) P3 and (d) P4 migration paths calculated with the
 354 CI-NEB method. The colour code for the atoms is the same as in Fig. 3. For P4 migration
 355 path (d), the colour of the sphere representing the positions of the hopping oxygen has been
 356 changed along the path, in order to highlight the migration from O1 to O2 crystallographic
 357 site.

358 The migration paths and the corresponding transition states were obtained by means of the
 359 climbing-image nudged elastic band (CI-NEB) method [49, 50]. A schematic of the
 360 individuated migration paths is reported in Fig. 4. The geometry of the ground state of the
 361 pristine and the defective structures, and the geometry of the transition states were used to

362 calculate the corresponding phonon frequencies and to extract the relevant quantities entering
363 the definition of the diffusion coefficient (Eq. 9).

364 3. Results and discussion

365 Fig. 5 illustrates the XRD patterns of the three Mayenite samples (CA, CCA, CAA),
366 confirming $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ as the primary phase, with CaO and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ identified as secondary
367 phases. In detail, Rietveld refinement analysis of each diffraction pattern revealed that sample
368 CA contained 66.7 wt% of $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$, with the remainder comprising of 31.1 wt% of CaO,
369 and 2.3 wt% of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (Fig. S1). Sample CCA contained 64.4 wt% of $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$, 6.3 wt%
370 CaO, and 29.3 wt% of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (Fig. S2), and finally sample CAA contained 68.3 wt% of
371 $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$, 14 wt% CaO and 17.7 wt% of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (Fig. S3). This indicates, that the three
372 different molar ratios of Ca/Al used during synthesis did not make any significant difference
373 in the obtained yield of $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$. The CaO phase in all three samples originates as an
374 unreacted product of reaction (III), whereas $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is spontaneously formed when CaO is
375 exposed to any moisture from the environment. Hence, the diffraction peak assigned to
376 $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is very broad, indicating a very low crystallinity, as expected.

377 The proposed synthesis mechanisms of $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$ are outlined below. Firstly, the calcium
378 and aluminium salts are converted to their corresponding hydroxides during precipitation
379 (reaction I and II). While during aging, these hydroxides convert to their respective oxides (I,
380 II), and finally during the calcination process to Mayenite (III). By products of the synthesis
381 process such as NaCl and NaNO_3 are easily removed while rinsing the precipitates with
382 distilled water.

386

387

Fig. 5 XRD patterns of the as-prepared Mayenite samples

388 The chemical states of the as-prepared Mayenite samples were analyzed by XPS and are
 389 illustrated in Fig. 6. In more detail, the high resolution spectra of Ca 2p is presented in Fig
 390 6(a, d, g) exhibiting two peaks corresponding to Ca 2p_{1/2} at ~350 eV and Ca 2p_{3/2} at ~346 eV,
 391 with difference of ~ 3.5 eV. These peaks are indicative of Ca²⁺ ions [51]. On the other hand,

402 **Fig. 6** XPS spectra of Ca2p, Al2p and O1s for Mayenite samples, CA (a,b,c), CCA (d,e,f)
 403 and CAA (g,h,i).

404

405 **Table 3** Binding energy values in eV for all three Mayenite samples; determined by XPS

406 407 408 409 Mayenite e samples	O1s			Al2p	Ca2p	
	Al-O	Ca-O	-OH	O-Al	Ca 2p1/2	Ca 2p3/2
CA	531.04	529.8	532.41	72.53	345.88	349.31
CCA	531.26	530.2 4	532.75	72.91	346.4	349.92
CAA	531.43	530.4 7	532.52	73.03	346.51	350.08

410 Fig. 7 shows the SEM and TEM images of CA, CCA and CAA nanoparticles along with their
 411 size distribution. CA and CAA show relatively dispersed nanoparticles while CCA exhibits
 412 agglomerated and bigger nanoparticles as it can be seen in both SEM and TEM images. The
 413 particle size and agglomeration can be linked to Ca/Al molar ratios used during synthesis.
 414 The higher Ca/Al ratio speeds up the rate of calcium hydration and starts the Mayenite
 415 crystallization sooner, resulting in bigger particles. Average particle size of CA was
 416 calculated as 217 nm with a size distribution range from 105 to 338 nm. Average particle size
 417 of CCA was calculated as 287 nm with a size distribution range from 133 to 446 nm. Average
 418 particle size of CAA was calculated as 255 nm with a size distribution range from 88 to 462
 419 nm. All three samples exhibit a predominantly spherical shape with some variations.

420

421 **Fig. 7** Mayenite samples SEMs (a,b,c), TEMs (d,e,f), and particle size distribution obtained
 422 from the SEM images (g,h,i)

423

424 Table 4 represents the BET surface area of CA, CCA and CAA. CAA exhibits the highest
 425 BET surface area of 7.5 m²/g while CCA shows the lowest surface area of 6.4 m²/g. CAA has
 426 smaller and dispersed nanoparticles, providing higher surface area.

427

428

429 **Table 4** BET surface area of Mayenite samples

430

431	Sample	BET Surface area (m ² /g)
432	Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -I (CA)	6.9 ± 0.7
433	Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -II (CCA)	6.4 ± 0.6
434	Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₃ -III (CAA)	7.5 ± 0.8

435 Fig. 8 represents simultaneously performed TGA and DSC plots of Limestone to determine
436 the operating temperature for thermochemical cycling. The process was divided into three
437 steps, firstly, heating Limestone from room temperature to 1000 °C under N₂ environment
438 (orange) then kept isothermal for 30 min under N₂/CO₂ atmosphere (red) and finally cooled
439 down to room temperature under N₂/CO₂ environment (green). During the heating process,
440 the calcination started at 723 °C and reached its peak at 850 °C, resulting in a total weight
441 loss of 44%. This loss represents the evolution of CO₂ during decomposition of CaCO₃ to
442 CaO. Because no CO₂ evolution or absorption happened during the isothermal step, no
443 weight change was observed. During the cooling step, the carbonation reaction started at 868
444 °C and peaked at 842.5 °C, and led to total weight gain of 27% due to CaO conversion to
445 CaCO₃. This gain is 17 p.p. less than the weight loss during the calcination reaction,
446 indicating an incomplete carbonation reaction. Instead of selecting different temperatures for
447 the calcination and carbonation steps during thermochemical cycling, we opted for a single
448 higher peak temperature (850 °C) to simplify the process.

449

450 **Fig. 8** Simultaneous TGA-DSC analysis of Limestone with calcination and carbonation peak
 451 temperatures

452

453 The effective conversions of pure Limestone and the Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples
 454 against their number of cycles are presented in Fig. 9. Pure Limestone exhibited an effective
 455 conversion of 0.150 after 40 cycles which is the lowest among all other mixture samples. Out
 456 of the 5% Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples, 5CAA performed the best, achieving an
 457 effective conversion of 0.383, 2.5 times higher than pure Limestone. For the 10%
 458 Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples, 10CAA performed the best, with effective conversions
 459 of 0.335. In the 20% Mayenite samples, 20CAA stood out as the top performer, achieving
 460 effective conversions of 0.375. Overall, out of the three Mayenite additives, CAA turned out
 461 to be the best additive irrespective of Mayenite percentage.

462

463

464

466 **Fig. 9** Effective conversion against number of cycles for Limestone and Mayenite-Limestone
 467 samples: a) 5% Mayenite b) 10% Mayenite and c) 20% Mayenite.

468 The energy storage density of all samples at the 40th cycle is shown in Fig. 10. The error bars
 469 represent the standard deviation of energy storage values. The sample CAA (green) and CCA
 470 (blue) exhibited a relatively stable performance while the sample CA (red) showed
 471 inconsistent energy storage performance as shown by their standard deviations. Overall CAA
 472 sample not only demonstrates stable energy storage performance but also higher energy
 473 density values. After 40 cycles, 5CAA out-performed all the samples, exhibiting the highest
 474 energy storage density of 1137 kJ/kg, 2.5 times higher than the energy storage density of pure
 475 Limestone (455 kJ/kg). This value of energy storage density for sample 5CAA is significantly
 476 higher even when compared to other promising reported additives in the literature showing
 477 the great potential of Mayenite. For example, the energy storage density of the
 478 ZrO_2/Al_2O_3 additive reported in the literature was 675 kJ/kg [55], of the ZrO_2 additive was
 479 455 kJ/kg and for Al_2O_3 was 782 kJ/kg [32].

480

481

482 **Fig. 10** Energy storage density of Limestone and Mayenite-Limestone samples at 40th cycle

483

484 To gain a deeper understanding of the additive influence on the calcination reaction, the
 485 activation energies were calculated for both pure Limestone and 5CAA. Fig. 11 depicts the
 486 DSC measurements of pure Limestone and 5CAA during the calcination reaction, carried out
 487 at heating rates of 5, 10, and 20 °C/min, accompanied by their respective Kissinger plots. The
 488 peak temperature for pure Limestone was observed at 815 °C, 841 °C, and 868 °C for heating
 489 rates of 5, 10, and 20 °C/min, respectively. Similarly, the peak temperature for 5CAA was
 490 registered at 804 °C, 827 °C, and 863 °C for heating rates of 5, 10, and 20 °C/min,
 491 respectively.

492

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496

499 **Fig. 11** DSC measurements for calcination reaction of 5CAA(a) and Limestone (c) at three
 500 different heating rates, along with their corresponding Kissinger plots 5CAA(b) and
 501 Limestone (d)

502 The activation energy for the calcination reaction of pure Limestone was calculated at 195
 503 kJ/mol, while for 5CAA, it was calculated as 168 kJ/mol. The incorporation of the CAA
 504 additive demonstrated an enhancement in reaction kinetics, evident in the lower activation
 505 energy observed for 5CAA.

507 **Fig. 12** Reaction characteristics of Limestone and 5CAA in the 2nd and 40th cycle; (a)
 508 effective conversion, (b) calcination reaction rates, and (c) carbonation reaction rates

509 Fig. 12 illustrates the reaction characteristics of Limestone and 5CAA during the 2nd and 40th
510 cycles, containing effective conversions, carbonation reaction rates, and calcination reaction
511 rates. Since the 1st calcination cycle was not an isothermal reaction, as it started before the
512 temperature reached 850 °C, the 2nd cycle was considered for the reaction kinetics study
513 presented below. The carbonation reaction proceeds in two distinct phases: a chemical
514 reaction-controlled phase, characterized by rapid CO₂ adsorption, and a diffusion-controlled
515 phase, where CO₂ adsorption occurs slower. 5CAA exhibits higher effective conversions in
516 the 40th cycle during calcination and carbonation (Fig. 12a). In the 2nd cycle, Limestone
517 exhibits greater calcination reaction rates compared to 5CAA, whereas in the 40th cycle,
518 5CAA demonstrates higher calcination rates than Limestone (Fig. 12b). During the second
519 cycle, CAA additive nanoparticles were being dispersed within the Limestone grains,
520 effectively activating the CAA additive. The comparison of carbonation rates indicates that
521 5CAA exhibits higher rates than Limestone for both cycles (Fig. 12c). Overall 5CAA shows
522 improved CO₂ adsorption and diffusion capacity as compared to Limestone.

524 **Fig. 13** Carbonation reaction calculations for Limestone and 5CAA in two phases during the
 525 2nd and 40th cycle; (a) chemical reaction controlled phase, (b) diffusion controlled phase.

526

527 The carbonation kinetic analysis of 5CAA and Limestone during both the chemical reaction-
 528 controlled and diffusion-controlled phases is illustrated in Fig. 13. Table 5 presents the
 529 carbonation kinetic parameters, including K_C and K_D , which are determined by fitting the
 530 curves in Figure 13 (a) and (b), respectively. These parameters play a crucial role in
 531 interpreting the carbonation reaction process, particularly in differentiating between the
 532 chemical reaction-controlled and diffusion-controlled phases [40]. The close agreement
 533 between the results obtained from the kinetic model and the fitting outcomes (with an R^2
 534 value approximately equal to 0.99) validates the suitability of the shrinking core model for
 535 describing and analyzing the carbonation reaction process for both samples.

536

537 **Table 5**

Sample	N	K_C	R^2	$K_D \times 10^3$	R^2
CaCO ₃	2	0.12217	0.982	0.93979	0.998
5CAA	2	0.10964	0.976	1.87959	0.997
CaCO ₃	40	0.06579	0.983	0.09398	0.988
5CAA	40	0.08771	0.981	0.62653	0.992

538 K_C and K_D values for Limestone and 5CAA during 2nd and 40th cycle

539

540

541

542

543

544 Notably, the K_C and K_D values of 5CAA significantly exceed those of Limestone during 40th
 545 cycles. After 40 cycles, the K_C and K_D value for 5CAA is 1.33 and 6.67 times than those for
 546 Limestone, respectively. The higher K_C and K_D values indicate a higher CO_2 adsorption
 547 capacity and lower CO_2 diffusion resistance, respectively. Consequently, 5CAA demonstrates
 548 superior CO_2 adsorption and diffusion capacity, facilitating the adsorption of CO_2 by CaO.
 549 To further understand the carbonation reaction mechanism of the 5CAA sample when
 550 compared to pure Limestone, the diffusion coefficient for each migration path, was calculated
 551 according to Eq. 9 at selected temperature values, and the corresponding plots are reported in
 552 Fig. 14.

553 **Fig. 14** Calculated diffusion coefficients as a function of the temperature for the Ca^{2+} ion
 554 along the P1 migration path, and for the O^{2-} ions along the P2, P3 and P4 migration paths; the
 555 y-axis is on a \log_{10} scale. The dashed lines represent the fit of the data according to Eq. 11,
 556 with fitting parameters D_0 and ΔH_m^{eff} reported in Table 6.

557 By inspecting Fig. 14, it is possible to observe that the data can be fitted with an expression
 558 derived on the model of Eq. 9 of the kind below,

$$559 \quad D(T) = D_{eff} \left(\frac{-\Delta H_m^{eff}}{k_b T} \right) \quad (11)$$

560 where D_0 and ΔH_m^{eff} are a prefactor and an effective migration enthalpy, respectively. The
 561 fitted values for each migration path are reported in Table 6, together with the migration
 562 enthalpy ΔH_m values for comparison.

563

564

565 **Table 6.**

566 Calculated prefactor (D_0), effective migration enthalpy (ΔH_m^{eff}) and migration enthalpy
 567 (ΔH_m) for the considered migration paths of the Ca^{2+} (P1) and O^{2-} (P2-P4) ions.

path	D_{eff} (m^2/s)	ΔH_m^{eff} (kcal/mol)	ΔH_m (kcal/mol)
P1	8.75E-12	0.031	38.28
P2	1.19E-10	0.059	36.90
P3	8.93E-10	0.063	40.13
P4	4.37E-10	0.057	34.59

568

569 If only migration enthalpies (ΔH_m) were taken into account (Table 6), it might lead to
 570 conclude that the O^{2-} ions diffuse faster than the Ca^{2+} ions via the P4 diffusion path. However,
 571 the migration enthalpies are calculated as static (CI-NEB) potential energy barriers, thus
 572 neglecting the effect of the temperature (see ‘‘Ionic conductivity’’ section in the
 573 supplementary information); indeed, the temperature plays an essential role in the ionic
 574 conduction. In fact, once the temperature is taken into account, the effective migration
 575 enthalpy (ΔH_m^{eff}) for the Ca^{2+} species turns out to be about half of the effective migration
 576 enthalpy for the O^{2-} species, regardless the kind of oxygen migration path. This indicates that
 577 the Ca^{2+} ions diffuse faster than the O^{2-} ions, with larger diffusion coefficient throughout the

578 considered temperature range – this can be seen by inspecting Fig. 14, where the diffusion
579 coefficient values of the Ca^{2+} atoms are larger than those of the O^{2-} atoms at each of the
580 considered temperature values and irrespective of the oxygen diffusion path. This means that
581 the enhanced carbonation reaction of sample 5CAA when compared to pure Limestone is
582 attributed to the dual ability of Mayenite to first allow CO_2 absorption and then diffusion
583 through the grains; and second promote the migration of Ca^{2+} ions responsible for the
584 formation of CaCO_3 . It is uncertain though to which extent CO_2 absorption and diffusion is
585 comparable to Ca^{2+} migration for the formation of CaCO_3 .

586 The inertness of Mayenite was confirmed by comparing the XRD patterns of all mixture
587 samples before and after thermochemical cycling (Fig. 12, S4, S5). Fig. 15 represents the
588 XRD patterns of 20 wt% Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples before (a) and after cycling
589 (b). In as-prepared samples the Limestone exhibits sharp peaks, suppressing its crystalline
590 nature, while the lower peak intensity of Mayenite corresponds to its overall lower percentage
591 in the sample. In contrast, in samples after cycling (Fig. 15b), the Limestone phase
592 experiences a decline in its pure crystallinity, while the Mayenite phase retains both its phase
593 and crystalline characteristics. This phase retention confirms the inertness of Mayenite during
594 cycling. As cycling was concluded on the carbonation step, Limestone peaks are reflected in
595 the samples obtained after cycling. The presence of CaO phase indicates incomplete
596 carbonation reaction at the end of the 40th cycle.

598 **Fig. 15** XRD patterns for 20% Mayenite samples a) As-prepared b) After-cycling

599

600 SEM micrographs of the pure Limestone and 5CAA sample (the best performer), before and
 601 after thermochemical cycling are presented in Fig. 16. It is evident that after cycling, the pure
 602 Limestone sample exhibits similar morphology to the 5CAA sample with relatively dispersed
 603 particles, exhibiting higher surface area. Moreover, the SEM micrographs of the other

604 Limestone/Mayenite mixture samples after cycling also show similar morphology when
605 compared to the pure Limestone sample (Fig. S6, S7, S8). In order to further investigate the
606 morphological changes of the pure Limestone sample and the best performing one (5CAA)
607 before and after cycling, nitrogen adsorption analysis was performed. Interestingly, both
608 samples exhibited very similar values of BET specific surface areas and BJH pore volumes
609 before and after cycling, as presented in Table S1. In detail, the specific surface area of pure
610 Limestone and of 5CAA before cycling was 13.1 and 9.9 m²/g, respectively. After cycling,
611 their specific surface area increased to 72.7 m²/cm for pure Limestone and 70.0 m²/g for
612 5CAA, as evident from the corresponding SEM micrographs. This indicates that the
613 improvement of Limestone with the addition of Mayenite upon cycling is purely due to the
614 better diffusion of CO₂ and Ca²⁺ among the Limestone grains, essential for the carbonation
615 reaction, and not because of the prevention of sintering and pore plugging. This information
616 is critical for designing new additives for enhancing the thermochemical energy storage
617 performance of Limestone, demonstrating the importance of their chemical composition

618 which is linked to their material properties.
619 **Fig. 16** SEM micrographs of Limestone and 5CAA samples; as-prepared and after cycling.

620

621 The distribution of Mayenite across the sample was examined through EDS mapping. Fig. 17
622 illustrates the EDS mapping of the 5CAA sample in its as-prepared and post-cycling states.
623 Despite having only 5 wt% Mayenite, both samples exhibit a significant presence of
624 aluminum. In as-prepared samples, Mayenite particles were sitting on the surface of
625 Limestone particles. The post-cycling EDS mapping of the 5CAA sample unveils a
626 homogeneous distribution of Mayenite (Al) throughout the samples. This uniform
627 distribution is attributed to the diffusion of Mayenite occurring during the cycling.

629 **Fig. 17** EDS mapping of as-prepared and after cycling 5CAA sample

630 **3. Conclusions**

631 In conclusion, the addition of Mayenite as an additive to Limestone for thermochemical
632 energy storage has been shown to significantly enhance the performance of Limestone as a
633 TCES system. Mayenite additives contributed to faster reaction kinetics during both the
634 calcination and carbonation processes of Limestone during cycling. The performance of
635 Mayenite/Limestone mixture samples varied depending on the percentage of Mayenite added.
636 While all Mayenite percentages showed improvements over pure Limestone, the optimal
637 performance was observed in the sample containing 5wt% Mayenite (with a lower Ca/Al
638 ratio), suggesting an optimal additive concentration for maximizing energy storage
639 performance linked to the improved Ca^{2+} and CO_2 diffusion through the Limestone grains.
640 Overall, the findings of this study demonstrate the potential of Mayenite as a promising
641 additive for boosting the thermochemical energy storage performance of Limestone. The
642 enhanced energy storage capacity, coupled with improved cycling stability and reaction
643 kinetics, positions Mayenite as a valuable candidate for advancing the development of long-
644 duration energy storage systems, essential for the integration of renewable energy sources
645 into the grid. Further research and optimization efforts may focus on fine-tuning the
646 Mayenite/Limestone composition and as well exploring other cycling conditions such as
647 higher than 1 bar of CO_2 pressure which may further enhance the carbonation reaction
648 kinetics.

649

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660

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